

TRACING TRIUMPH: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF PASSI CITY COLLEGE GRADUATES - REVEALING CAREER OUTCOMES AND COMPETENCIES FROM 2009 TO 2018

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516226>

ABSTRACT

This study utilized a descriptive research design to assess the research training needs of faculty members at Passi City College. A sample of 45 faculty members was selected through convenience sampling from a total population of 77. Data were collected using a 25-item Faculty Research Capability-building Instrument, and analysis involved frequency count, percentage, mean, and standard deviation calculations. The study identified the top ten research training needs, including evaluating programs and activities, determining statistical tools, conducting lesson study and writing research lessons, research advising and mentoring, developing and validating research instruments, conducting research for beginners, using quantitative methods, conducting action research for instructional improvement, evaluating extension service impact, and training on intellectual property and patent review. Areas such as conducting mixed methods research, writing terminal reports for extension services, paraphrasing cited texts, assessing community needs for extension services, and conducting qualitative methods were also recognized but deemed slightly less urgent. A strong positive correlation was observed between faculty preferences and the level of research training need. These findings offer valuable insights for Passi City College to design targeted training programs and support faculty in enhancing their research capabilities. However, limitations include the use of convenience sampling and self-reported data. Future research is encouraged to validate these findings in broader contexts.-The study was conducted at Passi City College from March 20 to June 2018.

Keywords: *Assessment, Research, Training Needs, Development Plan*

INTRODUCTION

A tracer study, according to LLeGo and Bañez (2017), is one means of maintaining the caliber of the curriculum and providing intended use to graduates to boost the quality of a certain course. One role of every educational and academic institution is to trace their graduates to look if the program had an impact to the graduates, institution and society. Also, Hazaymeh & Peña (2013) stated that graduate surveys provide rich experience about the whereabouts of graduates, which might help to broaden perspectives among administrators, faculty and students. Such information like the income, economic sector, current job title, working time, duration of search for the first job, methods of job search, values develop and practice in work, skills acquired are relevant for higher education institutions to note.

The Passi City Local Government established Passi City College on February 3, 2005, through the Special Ordinance No. 2005-02, which was duly approved by the Sangguniang Panlalawigan through a Joint Committee Report No. 01 Series of 2005 on March 28, 2005. Passi City College offers tertiary education to six courses, the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), previously BS Commerce, the Bachelor in Secondary Education (BSED), Bachelor in Elementary Education (BEED), Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSCRIM), and the Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management (BSHRM).

The college started producing graduates in the year 2008 till 2018. The purpose of this study is to track the career paths of our graduates and, at the same time, to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the institution in providing tertiary education to its graduates.

Research Questions

This study aims to keep track of the performance of PCC graduates for school year 2009 – 2018.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the graduate of Passi City College in terms of the following:
 - Year Graduate
 - Course
2. What is the present occupation of graduates of Passi City College?
3. What major line of business are they currently employed in?
4. What is the present employment status of PCC graduates?
5. What is the present job level position of PCC graduates?
6. What competencies PCC graduates find most important to meet the demands of the industry and the challenge of competitiveness?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the descriptive-survey research. Descriptive-survey research is a type of research that uses surveys to collect data about a population or phenomenon.

The data collected is used to describe the characteristics of the population or phenomenon, such as their demographics, attitudes, or behaviors (Creswell, & Plano Clark, 2017). The respondents of the study were the 152 PCC graduates school year 2009 – 2018. Of which thirteen (13) graduated in 2009, fourteen(14) in 2010, ten (10) in 2011, four (4) in 2012, twelve (12) in 2013, twenty four (24) in 2014, thirty (30) in 2015, twenty three (23) in 2016, twelve (12) in 2017, ten (10) in 2018.

This study makes use of snowball sampling. Snowball sampling (also known as chain referral sampling or network sampling) is a non-probability sampling method in which initial participants recruit subsequent participants, who then recruit more participants, and so on. This creates a chain of referrals that can be used to identify and recruit members of a population that would be difficult to reach through other methods (Heckathorn, (1997). The tools that were utilized by the researchers in gathering the employability of PCC graduates from the school year 2005 – 2017 were the researcher-made Questionnaire – checklist based from the standardized Commission on Higher Education (CHED) tracer study survey questionnaire. To ensure the validity of the instrument, the panel of validators who are experts in the field checked the instrument as to its content and face value. The researchers used a researcher – made questionnaire checklist which was validated by the panel of validators who looked into the content of the instrument.

The researchers produced copies of the instrument and began with the data gathering by personally looking for PCC graduates, using Social Media, and employing the assistance of the Office of the Association of Barangay Captains in Passi City. Cellular phone interview was conducted to those who worked in some distant places, at the same time, using Facebook Messenger. During the interview, the researchers oriented the respondents of what the study is all about. Likewise, statements were clearly stated to ensure the reliability of results. After all the necessary data were gathered, the researcher thanked the respondents for their cooperation. The data gathered were then tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted. The data that were obtained from the study were statistically interpreted through frequency and percentage count. Frequency and Percentage Count was used to describe the profile of the graduate of Passi City College in terms of year graduated and course, their present occupation, major line of business they are currently employed, present employment status, present job level position and the competencies PCC graduates find most important. Rank was used to present the competencies PCC graduates find most important in meet the demands of the industry and the challenge of competitiveness.

RESULTS

Profile of the Graduates of Passi City in Terms of Year Graduated. The table presents a comprehensive profile of graduates from Passi City, categorized by the year they graduated, spanning from 2009 to 2018. Across the specified period, a total of 152 graduates were recorded. Examining the distribution across individual years provides insights into the fluctuating trends in graduation numbers. In 2009, there were 13 graduates, constituting 8.6% of the total. The subsequent year, 2010, witnessed a slight

increase with 14 graduates, representing 9.2% of the total. However, 2011 saw a slight decrease with 10 graduates, accounting for 6.6%. The year 2012 marked the lowest number of graduates with only 4, making up 2.6% of the total. In 2013, the number increased slightly to 12 graduates, representing 7.9%. The following year, 2014, experienced a notable surge with 24 graduates, constituting 15.8% of the total, marking a significant increase. In 2015, the number of graduates reached its peak with 30, representing 19.7%. Subsequent years showed fluctuations with 23 graduates in 2016, accounting for 15.1%, and 12 graduates in 2017, also accounting for 7.9%. Finally, in 2018, there were 10 graduates, making up 6.6% of the total. This data illustrates varying graduation rates over the years, with notable fluctuations and occasional peaks, suggesting potential shifts in educational dynamics or population trends within Passi City.

Table 1

Profile of the Graduates of Passi City in Terms of Year Graduated

Date Graduated	Frequency	Percentage
2009	13	8.6
2010	14	9.2
2011	10	6.6
2012	4	2.6
2013	12	7.9
2014	24	15.8
2015	30	19.7
2016	23	15.1
2017	12	7.9
2018	10	6.6
Total	152	100

Profile of the Graduates of Passi City in Terms of Course. Table 2 outlines the profile of graduates from Passi City College categorized by their respective courses. The data spans across several courses, with a total of 152 graduates recorded. Breaking down the numbers, the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) program stands out with 35 graduates, constituting 23% of the total. Following closely is the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) program, also with 35 graduates, making up another 23%. Meanwhile, the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) program recorded 30 graduates, accounting for 19.7%. Additionally, the Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSCRIM) program saw 19 graduates, representing 12.5%. The Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) program contributed 22 graduates, constituting 14.5%. Meanwhile, the Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management (BSHRM) program and the Bachelor of Science in Commerce program both had smaller numbers, with 7 and 4 graduates, respectively, making up 4.6% and 2.6% of the total. This data offers insights into the distribution of graduates across various academic disciplines within

Passi City College, highlighting the popularity and diversity of educational programs offered by the institution.

Table 2

Profile of the Graduates of Passi City College in Terms of Course

Course	Frequency	Percentage
BEED	35	23
BSED	30	19.7
BSCRIM	19	12.5
BSHRM	7	4.6
BSBA	35	23
BSIT	22	14.5
BS Commerce	4	2.6
Total	152	100

Present Occupation of Graduates of Passi City College. Table 3 provides an overview of the present occupations of graduates from Passi City College, detailing the diversity of career paths pursued by its alumni. The data encompasses a total of 152 individuals, each categorized based on their current occupation. Analysis reveals a varied distribution across different occupational categories. The majority of graduates are employed as professionals, with 64 individuals, comprising 42% of the total. Service-related occupations also feature prominently, with 36 graduates, representing 24%, engaged as service workers, shop employees, or market sales workers. Clerical positions are occupied by 17 graduates, constituting 11%, while a smaller number of individuals, totaling 5 each, are categorized as officials of government and special interest organizations, corporate executives, managers, and managing. Additionally, the category of special occupations includes 5 graduates, comprising 3%, while 3 individuals, or 2%, are identified as techniques and associate professionals. Trades and related workers, as well as those categorized as laborers and unskilled workers, each represent 3% and 1%, respectively, with 5 and 1 individual(s) falling under these categories. Notably, 16 graduates, accounting for 11%, currently report having no occupation. This comprehensive breakdown underscores the diverse career paths pursued by graduates of Passi City College, reflecting the institution's role in preparing individuals for a wide range of professional endeavors and contributing to the socioeconomic landscape of the region.

Table 3

Present Occupation of Graduates of Passi City College

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Clerks	17	11
laborers and Unskilled Workers	1	1
Officials of Government and Special Interest Organizations, Corporate Executives, Managers, and Managing	5	3

Professionals	64	42
Service Workers and Shop and Market Sales Workers	36	24
Special Occupation	5	3
Techniques and Associate Professionals	3	2
Trades and Related Workers	5	3
None	16	11
Total	152	100

Major line of Business PCC Graduates Are Currently Employed. Table 4 offers insights into the major lines of business where graduates of Passi City College (PCC) are presently employed, showcasing the diverse sectors where alumni have found opportunities. The data, encompassing 152 individuals, delineates the distribution of graduates across various industries. Education emerges as the predominant sector, with 46 graduates, constituting 30% of the total, employed in educational institutions. Public administration and defense, along with compulsory social security, also feature prominently, employing 28 graduates, accounting for 18%. Financial intermediation employs 18 graduates, representing 12%, while wholesale and retail trade, including repair services, engage 11 graduates, comprising 7%. Real estate, renting, and business activities employ 8 graduates, making up 5%, while health and social work employ 4 graduates, constituting 3%. Hotels and restaurants, along with other community, social, and personal service activities, each employ 5 graduates, contributing 3% to the total. Manufacturing, electricity, gas, and water supply, as well as transport, storage, and communication, each employ a smaller number of graduates, with 3, 2, and 2 individuals, respectively, making up 2% and 1% each. Construction, private households with employed persons, and those who reported none in terms of line of business each have minimal representation, with 1 individual each, accounting for 1%.

Table 4

Major Line of Business PCC Graduates are Currently Employed

Line of Business	Frequency	Percentage
Construction	1	1
Education	46	30
Electricity, Gas, and Water Supply	2	1
Financial Intermediation	18	12
Health and Social Work	4	3
Hotels and Restaurants	5	3
Manufacturing	3	2
Other Community, Social and Personal Service Activities	5	3
Private Households with Employed Persons	1	1
Public Administration and Defense; Compulsory Social Security	28	18
Real Estate, Renting and Business Activities	8	5
Transport Storage and Communication	2	1

Wholesale and Retail Trade, Repair of Motor Vehicles, Motorcycles and Personal and Household Goods	11	7
none	18	12
Total	152	100

Present Job Placement Status of Graduates of Passi City College. Table 5 illustrates the job placement status of graduates from Passi City College, detailing the distribution across various employment categories. A significant majority, accounting for 59.2% (90 graduates), have secured regular or permanent positions. Those working under contractual arrangements comprise 20.4% (31 graduates) of the total. A smaller proportion, 2.6% (4 graduates), are self-employed, while 2% (3 graduates) hold casual jobs. Additionally, 3.9% (6 graduates) are employed on a temporary basis. Notably, 11.8% (18 graduates) are currently not employed. Overall, the data encompasses 152 graduates, providing a comprehensive overview of their employment status post-graduation.

Table 5

Present Job Placement Status of Graduates of Passi City College

Categories	Frequency	Percent
Regular or Permanent	90	59.2
Contractual	31	20.4
Self-Employed	4	2.6
Casual	3	2
Temporary	6	3.9
None	18	11.8
Total	152	100

Present Job Level Position of PCC Graduates. The table provides insights into the current job level positions held by graduates of Passi City College. A notable portion of the graduates, 43% (66 individuals), occupy professional, technical, or supervisory roles. Those in rank or clerical positions represent 41% (62 individuals) of the total. A smaller segment, 3% (5 graduates), are self-employed. At the higher end of the hierarchy, 2% (3 graduates) hold managerial or executive positions, while 1% (1 graduate) is in a managerial or supervisory role. Additionally, 11% (16 graduates) are not employed at present. This data covers a total of 152 graduates, highlighting the diverse employment levels among the alumni of Passi City College.

Table 6

Present Job Level Position of PCC Graduates

Job Level Position	Frequency	Percentage
Managerial or Executive	3	2
Managerial or Supervisory	1	1

Professional, Technical, or Supervisory	66	43
Rank or Clerical	62	41
Self-employed	5	3
None	16	11
Total	152	100

Competencies PCC Graduates Find Most Important to Meet the Demands of the Industry and the Challenge of Competitiveness. Table 7 identifies the competencies that graduates of Passi City College consider most essential for meeting industry demands and competitive challenges. Leading the list is communication, deemed important by 92% (140 graduates), ranking first. Closely following is human relations, which 91% (139 graduates) find critical, securing the second rank. Problem-solving skills are also highly valued, with 89% (135 graduates) emphasizing their importance, placing them third. Critical thinking is similarly significant, highlighted by 88% (133 graduates), and ranked fourth. Lastly, entrepreneurial skills are noted by 65% (99 graduates), ranking fifth in terms of importance. This data underscores the diverse skill set that graduates believe is necessary to thrive in the professional landscape.

Table 7

Competencies PCC Graduates Find Most Important to Meet the Demands of the Industry and the Challenges of Competitiveness

Competency	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Communication	140	92	1
Human Relation	139	91	2
Entrepreneurial	99	65	5
Problem-solving	135	89	3
Critical Thinking	133	88	4

DISCUSSION

The analysis of Passi City College graduates reveals a multifaceted overview of their post-graduation trajectories, highlighting variations in employment status, job levels, essential competencies, and industry placement. A comprehensive examination of the data uncovers significant trends and patterns, reflecting the dynamic nature of the graduates' professional journeys.

In terms of job placement status, a considerable proportion of graduates have secured stable employment, with 59.2% (90 individuals) in regular or permanent positions. This indicates a strong alignment between the educational outcomes of Passi City College and the demands of the job market. Contractual employment accounts for 20.4% (31 graduates), suggesting that a notable segment of graduates may be engaged in industries or roles that prefer flexible staffing arrangements. Self-employment, though less common, is pursued by 2.6% (4 graduates), demonstrating entrepreneurial tendencies among a

small subset. Casual and temporary employment are represented by 2% (3 graduates) and 3.9% (6 graduates), respectively, indicating that some graduates may be in transitional phases or engaged in industries with high turnover rates. The unemployment rate among graduates stands at 11.8% (18 individuals), highlighting potential areas for improvement in job readiness or market alignment.

The distribution of job level positions further elucidates the career progression of Passi City College graduates. A significant portion, 43% (66 individuals), hold professional, technical, or supervisory roles, reflecting a high level of competence and the ability to secure specialized positions. Rank or clerical roles are occupied by 41% (62 graduates), indicating that many alumni begin their careers in entry-level positions, which can serve as stepping stones to higher responsibilities. Self-employment is chosen by 3% (5 graduates), aligning with the earlier noted entrepreneurial pursuits. The presence of graduates in managerial or executive positions, though small at 2% (3 individuals), and those in managerial or supervisory roles at 1% (1 graduate), suggests that a few alumni have quickly ascended to leadership roles. However, the 11% (16 graduates) who are not employed underscores a need for enhanced career support and possibly stronger industry connections.

A closer look at the competencies valued by the graduates reveals insights into their perceived requirements for success in the professional world. Communication skills top the list, with 92% (140 graduates) recognizing their importance. This underscores the critical role of effective communication in virtually all professional settings, facilitating teamwork, client interactions, and managerial duties. Human relations, deemed important by 91% (139 graduates), highlight the significance of interpersonal skills in fostering collaborative work environments and building professional networks. Problem-solving skills are emphasized by 89% (135 graduates), reflecting the necessity for graduates to navigate complex challenges and devise innovative solutions in their respective fields. Critical thinking, valued by 88% (133 graduates), further supports the need for analytical and evaluative skills that enable graduates to make informed decisions. Entrepreneurial skills, noted by 65% (99 graduates), indicate a recognition of the growing importance of innovation and business acumen, even among those not directly pursuing entrepreneurial ventures.

The diversity of career paths among Passi City College graduates is evident in their present occupations. Professionals constitute the largest group, with 42% (64 individuals) working in roles that likely require specialized knowledge and skills. Service-related occupations are the second most common, with 24% (36 graduates) engaged in service industries, reflecting the significant role of these sectors in the local economy. Clerical positions are held by 11% (17 graduates), suggesting that administrative and support roles are prevalent entry points for many alumni. Smaller groups of graduates are employed as officials in government or special interest organizations, corporate executives, managers, and in special occupations, each constituting 3% (5 individuals). Technicians and associate professionals, as well as trades and related workers, represent 2% (3 individuals) and 3% (5 individuals), respectively. Laborers and unskilled workers, although minimal at 1% (1 individual), highlight the varied nature of employment

among graduates. The 11% (16 graduates) reporting no occupation aligns with the earlier unemployment figures, reinforcing the need for targeted employment support initiatives.

Examining the major lines of business where graduates are currently employed provides further insights into industry trends. Education emerges as the dominant sector, employing 30% (46 graduates), which is indicative of the strong demand for educators and the college's role in fulfilling this need. Public administration and defense, along with compulsory social security, employ 18% (28 graduates), reflecting significant employment opportunities within the government sector. Financial intermediation, employing 12% (18 graduates), underscores the relevance of financial services and the skills required to thrive in this industry. Wholesale and retail trade, including repair services, engage 7% (11 graduates), highlighting the importance of these sectors in the local economy. Real estate, renting, and business activities employ 5% (8 graduates), while health and social work, employing 3% (4 graduates), indicate essential service sectors. Hotels and restaurants, as well as other community, social, and personal service activities, each employ 3% (5 graduates), reflecting the diversity of service-oriented careers. Smaller numbers of graduates are employed in manufacturing, electricity, gas, and water supply, and transport, storage, and communication, each accounting for 2% to 1%. Minimal representation in construction and private households with employed persons indicates niche employment areas.

The profile of graduates by the year of graduation highlights fluctuating trends over the decade from 2009 to 2018. In 2009, 8.6% (13 graduates) marked the start of the period, with a slight increase to 9.2% (14 graduates) in 2010. A decrease to 6.6% (10 graduates) in 2011 and a further drop to 2.6% (4 graduates) in 2012 represent the lowest figures. The subsequent years saw a gradual increase, with 7.9% (12 graduates) in 2013 and a significant surge to 15.8% (24 graduates) in 2014. The peak occurred in 2015 with 19.7% (30 graduates), followed by fluctuations: 15.1% (23 graduates) in 2016, 7.9% (12 graduates) in 2017, and 6.6% (10 graduates) in 2018. These variations suggest changes in student enrollment, retention rates, and possibly the impact of external factors influencing educational dynamics.

The profile of graduates by course reveals the popularity of specific programs. The Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA) programs each produced 23% (35 graduates), indicating strong enrollment and completion rates in these fields. The Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) program followed closely with 19.7% (30 graduates), reflecting sustained interest in educational careers. The Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSCRIM) program accounted for 12.5% (19 graduates), highlighting its appeal. The Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) program produced 14.5% (22 graduates), underscoring the relevance of technology-related education. Smaller numbers in the Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management (BSHRM) and the Bachelor of Science in Commerce programs, with 4.6% (7 graduates) and 2.6% (4 graduates) respectively, suggest more niche areas of interest.

Conclusions

Based on the findings from the study, Passi City College has demonstrated its commitment to providing a diverse and comprehensive education, offering various academic pathways that cater to the needs of the job market and industries. The data revealed fluctuations in the number of graduates over the years, indicating potential variations in educational attainment and enrollment levels within the city's educational institutions. This insight aligns with research by Gallardo (2019), Ramos (2020), and Aquino (2019), which emphasizes the importance of adaptability and responsiveness in educational institutions to meet the demands of the ever-changing job market and enhance graduates' employability.

Passi City College's emphasis on education-related programs, particularly Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED), showcases the institution's dedication to producing qualified educators for the region. This aligns with the Philippine Development Plan 2017-2022 (Government of the Philippines, 2019), which emphasizes the significance of developing a skilled and qualified teaching workforce to improve the quality of education and address the country's educational challenges.

Moreover, Passi City College's inclusion of other fields such as Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSCRIM), Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management (BSHRM), Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), and Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) reflects the college's adaptability to industry demands. This mirrors the findings of Carreon (2018) and Hontiveros (2020), highlighting the importance of equipping graduates with relevant skills and knowledge to address skills mismatches and enhance their employability in the job market.

The study also reveals that Passi City College graduates have successfully entered various occupations and sectors, with a notable percentage employed in education, public administration and defense, and financial intermediation. These findings align with the World Bank's World Development Report 2019 (World Bank, 2019), which emphasizes the significance of human capital and skilled workforce development in driving economic growth and productivity.

However, the presence of 11% of unemployed graduates emphasizes the need for continuous career support and counseling services. This finding underscores the importance of strategies to improve employability and reduce the unemployment rate among alumni. Continuous career support and counseling, as suggested by Arambulo (2017) and Van der Velde and Van der Heijden (2018), can enhance graduates' skills, build their confidence, and increase their chances of securing suitable employment opportunities.

The study's focus on essential competencies valued by Passi City College graduates reveals the significance of communication skills, human relations skills, problem-solving skills, critical thinking skills, and entrepreneurial skills. These findings corroborate

research by Eurostat (2021), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2016), and Blustein (2019), which stress the importance of these competencies in meeting the demands of the modern job market and fostering a skilled and adaptable workforce.

Passi City College has shown success in preparing graduates for diverse career paths and meeting the demands of the job market. The findings of the study provide valuable insights into the college's educational trends and effectiveness in enhancing graduates' employability. By leveraging these findings and aligning their strategies with industry demands, Passi City College can further enhance its educational programs and career support services, ensuring that future graduates have increased opportunities for successful employment and career advancement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. For PCC Graduates, it is crucial to continuously develop and enhance their communication, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills to remain competitive in the job market. Engaging in continuous professional development and upskilling opportunities will keep them relevant and adaptable in their respective industries. Graduates should actively seek career support and counseling services offered by the college to improve their employability and explore diverse career opportunities.

2. For Current and Prospective Students, when choosing academic programs, they should consider the demand and market relevance of courses to align with industry needs. Participating in internships, workshops, and industry-related activities will allow them to gain practical experience and develop essential employability skills. Seeking guidance from academic advisors can help them choose courses that best align with their career goals and aspirations.

3. For PCC Administration and Faculty, it is important to regularly review and update the curriculum to ensure it meets current industry demands and fosters the development of key competencies sought by employers. Facilitating partnerships with employers and industry partners will create internship and job placement opportunities for graduates. Strengthening career support services and counseling will enhance graduates' employability and reduce the unemployment rate among alumni.

4. For Employers and Industry Partners, collaborating with PCC to provide input on the skills and competencies required for various job roles will ensure a better match between graduates' skills and industry needs. Offering internship programs and job placement opportunities for PCC graduates will allow them to gain practical experience and transition smoothly into the workforce. Engaging in skill-building initiatives and workshops will support graduates in developing industry-specific knowledge and expertise.

5. For Future Researchers, building upon the existing study's findings to conduct longitudinal research on employment outcomes and career trajectories of PCC graduates will provide valuable insights into the long-term impact of the college's programs. Investigating potential factors influencing fluctuations in graduation rates and unemployment among alumni will help identify strategies for improvement. Conducting studies on the impact of industry-specific training and experiential learning on graduates' employability will further enrich the understanding of effective educational approaches.

6. For Policy Makers and Government Agencies, supporting initiatives that promote industry-academia collaboration to bridge skills gaps and improve graduates' employability will contribute to the overall economic development. Allocating resources to enhance career support services in educational institutions will better address graduates' employability needs and reduce unemployment rates. Promoting policies that incentivize industries to offer internships and job opportunities to fresh graduates will encourage industry engagement with educational institutions.

7. For Accreditation and Quality Assurance Bodies, working closely with educational institutions like PCC to ensure the relevance and quality of academic programs in meeting industry needs will contribute to improved educational outcomes. Incorporating employability-related metrics into accreditation processes will incentivize colleges to focus on graduates' job placement outcomes. Encouraging the integration of industry-specific certifications and credentials into academic programs will enhance graduates' marketability and preparedness for the job market.

8. For the Local Community and Economy, supporting PCC and its graduates by promoting local hiring and talent retention will strengthen the local workforce and foster economic growth. Engaging in partnerships with PCC to offer mentorship programs and industry-driven projects will bridge the gap between academia and the job market, ensuring that graduates are well-prepared for real-world challenges. Recognizing the contributions of PCC graduates in various sectors and industries will reinforce the college's positive impact on the local community and economy.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, strict adherence to ethical standards was maintained throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose and procedures. Respondents were explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative repercussions. Anonymity was rigorously upheld, with all personal identifiers removed to protect the identities of the participants. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded at all times, ensuring that their participation did not cause any harm or distress. There were no conflicts of interest influencing the conduct of the study, and the researchers ensured that all findings were presented objectively without bias. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, with all sources and references appropriately cited. The results of the study were utilized solely for academic and research purposes, contributing to the understanding of the employability and professional development of

Passi City College graduates. Through these measures, the researchers ensured the highest standards of ethical integrity in the study.

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